

Evaluation of Mechanical Properties of Cement Grouted Bituminous Mix with Varied Types of Grouts

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Abstract The Cement Grouted Bituminous Mix (CGBM) is an innovative pavement technique that employs grouting materials to effectively fill the open-graded bituminous mix, characterized by a significant air void content. The application of Aggregate Gradation II refers to the standards outlined in IRC SP 125 (2019). Following these guidelines, bitumen mix preparation involves the utilization of bitumen with a VG 30 grade while assuring a void percentage ranging from 25% to 30%. The grouting materials utilized in this study are Portland cementitious grain (PG), ordinary Portland cementitious grain (OG), and rapid-hardening cementitious grain (RG). The bitumen mix samples have been enhanced with different grouts to develop grouted bitumen samples containing varied cement compositions. The Cement Grouted Bituminous Mix (CGBM) can be grouted using many types of cement, including Portland Pozzolana cement (PGBM), Ordinary Pozzolana cement (OGBM), and Rapid hardening cement (RGBM). The bitumen samples that had been grouted were then allowed to cure, and their strength properties were assessed using tests for durability (Cantabro test), indirect tensile strength, compressive strength, and Marshal stability at 3 and 28 days. The RGBM sample exhibited a comparatively higher percentage increase in characteristic strength than the PGBM and OGBM mixes. This can be attributed to the fact that the former had already attained a substantial portion of its strength after three days. However, it is worth noting that all samples showed nearly equivalent strength levels after 28 days. According to this study's findings, using RGBM for construction projects in colder climates with early strength requirements is recommended. The RGBM exhibits a comparatively greater strength of 9.10 N/mm² compared to the PGBM and OGBM, which have strengths of 8.92 and 8.06 N/mm², respectively. All the samples exhibit excellent stability values within the permissible range.

Keywords Cement Grouted Bituminous Mix (CGBM), Indirect Tensile Strength Test (ITS), Cantabro Test, Marshal stability test.

Introduction

The most used road pavements in India and worldwide are bituminous pavers and rigid concrete pavements. To address the limitations of both these pavement types while capitalizing on their advantages, the concept of Cement Grouted Bituminous Mix (CGBM) was developed. In the 1950s, CGBM was initially devised as a protective measure against waste oils and fuel infiltration on asphalt concrete surfaces in France. This innovative technique, pioneered by the French construction company Jean Lefebvre, sought a cost-effective alternative to concrete roads for maintenance. Over time, laboratory research and practical implementation of CGBM have demonstrated superior performance to traditional bituminous mixes. Pavements are typically classified into bituminous and concrete pavements based on the materials used in their construction. Concrete pavements have been employed to mitigate the issues of cracking and rutting deformations that afflict flexible pavements. However, due to their high construction costs, using concrete pavements for extensive and lengthy road stretches is often economically impractical. CGBM, also called Semi-flexible Pavements (SFP) by previous researchers, was developed as an effective solution to reduce construction costs and mitigate the problems associated with flexible pavements, particularly rutting and cracking deformations. The construction of CGBM involves preparing an open-graded bituminous mix with 25-35% air voids, followed by pouring a grout slurry over the bituminous mix. The grouting occurs when the mix temperature is reduced to 50-65°C or ambient temperature. Guidelines provided in IRC SP-125 (2019) offer detailed instructions for the design, preparation, and application procedures of CGBM laid over a bituminous surface. A single-graded bituminous mix is typically used and grouted with cement (Marg et al., 2019). CGBM offers several advantages over traditional pavements, including protection against damage caused by oil and gasoline spills, resistance to permanent deformation, reduced sensitivity to temperature variations compared to flexible pavements, impermeability, and improved traction. In various studies, CGBM has been recognized as a viable alternative to both asphalt and concrete pavements based on its unique properties and mechanical performance. The primary objective of this research is to provide a comprehensive analysis of semi-flexible pavement design, construction, and performance based on laboratory and field-scale testing. The research is conducted in two stages: the first stage focuses on the design methodology and laboratory-scale preparation. In contrast, the second stage assesses the performance of semi-flexible pavements under traffic loads and their resistance to fuel and oil spillage and longevity. Studies by Bharath et al. (2019) demonstrate that CGBM outperforms typical bituminous mixes in ITS, resilient modulus, dynamic modulus, and rutting. Full-depth grouting is observed in field core samples, and microcomputed tomography (Micro-CT) tests are conducted to evaluate the air void content and connectivity in the CGBM mix. While IRC SP-125 (2019) specifies tests for CGBM samples from field-cored and laboratory-prepared samples, it does not include durability tests like the Cantabro test using the Los Angeles abrasion testing machine, thus necessitating additional research in this area (Sunil & Naga Kumar, 2020). Furthermore,

Satyarnoa et al. (2014) research explores the mix design and flowability of different grout slurries with varying water-to-cement ratios. This study indicates that a higher minimum water-cement ratio (w/c min) or lower cement-water ratio is required to achieve a greater sand-cement ratio s/c (as required by the flow cone test). The maximum s/c ratio for coarse sand (zone II) is 1.5; for zone I gradation sand, it is 1.0, with an overall s/c ratio not exceeding 2.0, as per this study. Shukla et al. (2019) found CGBM is well-suited for wearing courses. Their research compares six cement-grouted bituminous mixes with varying aggregate gradations, compaction intensity, and grout composition. X-ray Micro Computed Tomography (XRμCT) tests on laboratory-prepared samples were used to analyze the air void content and interconnectivity. Field evaluations, such as measuring deflection using the Falling Weight Deflectometer method, show that the center deflection in the CGBM section is 48% lower than in the conventional bituminous section. The back-estimated resilient modulus (MR) of the CGBM layer is 5 to 6 times higher than the conventional bituminous layer, as determined through structural assessment using FWD (Shukla et al., 2021). The study by Koting et al. (2014) delves into the mechanical characteristics of cement-bitumen composites as a semi-flexible pavement surface material, revealing that substituting 5% of the cement with silica fume, along with the appropriate quantity of superplasticizer, enhances compressive strength and tensile stiffness modulus.

Methodology

The primary objective of this research is to ensure that the open-graded bituminous mix possesses an adequate volume of air voids to accommodate the various grout types utilized in this investigation. This is achieved by optimizing the grout slurry's flowability by selecting appropriate cement and sand components in line with the recommended volumetric mix ratios. The preparation of CGBM composite samples follows the specified guidelines. This process commences once the temperature reaches ambient levels or when the bituminous mix temperature drops to 50–60°C, when the mould is filled with the grout. After the sample preparation phase, a battery of tests is conducted, encompassing flow tests, abrasion tests, compressive strength tests, Marshall stability tests, and indirect tensile strength tests. Ultimately, a statistical analysis of sample composition is performed, evaluating the properties of the grout and comparing various CGBM mixes with different grout sample types. Fig 1 illustrates the schematic representation of the study's methodology. Bituminous mix preparation involves carefully considering aggregate and bitumen gradation considering various volumetric proportions of bituminous mixes. The preparation of the grout slurry hinges on selecting sand and cement in the appropriate proportion, ensuring a suitable water-to-cement ratio to achieve the desired flowability of the grout. CGBM composite samples are created by introducing grout into the moulds of the bituminous mix when the temperature falls within the range of 50–60°C. The durability assessment involves the execution of an Abrasive test. At the same time, the evaluation of strength encompasses the performance of Compressive strength tests, Marshall tests, flow tests, and Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) tests. Finally, a comprehensive analysis assesses different mixtures and proportions across various sample types.

Fig 1: Flowchart showing the methodology of the study.

Materials and their Properties

Aggregate Gradation

IRC SP-125-2019 prescribes three distinct open-graded gradations characterized by a higher proportion of coarse aggregates in the presence of both coarse and fine aggregates. Gradation – II, conforming to the specifications outlined in MoRTH (Ministry of Road Transport and Highways) guidelines and detailed in Table 1, has been selected for this study. It is worth noting that while this research primarily examines various types of cement for grout preparation, the other pertinent parameters remain constant throughout the study. To ensure the suitability of the aggregates for the chosen gradation, all aggregates are subjected to a thorough assessment of their physical properties as per the criteria specified in IRC SP 125-2019, as presented in Table 2 below. The aggregates' specific gravity and water absorption characteristics were determined to be 2.66 and 1.15%, respectively.

Table 1. Aggregate Gradation as per IRC SP-125 (2019)

IS Sieve Sizes (mm)	The cumulative percentage by weight of total aggregate passing
19	100
13.2	90-100
9.5	70-86
4.75	52-71
2.36	44-58
1.18	36-46
0.6	24-38
0.3	18-24
0.15	12-20
0.075	6-10

Table 2: Test results of aggregate

S.No	Test Performed	Codal Specification	Test Results	MoRTH SpecificationLimit
1	Impact Value (%)	IS:2386 Part 4	15.61	Max 24
2	Abrasion Value (%)	IS:2386 Part 4	32.52	Max 40
3	Flakiness Index (%)	IS:2386 Part 1	23.5	Max 30
4	Elongation Index (%)	IS:2386 Part 1	12.5	Max 15
5	Specific Gravity	IS:2386 Part 4	2.66	2.5-3.5
6	Water absorption (%)	IS:2386 Part 3	1.15	Max 2

Bitumen

Bitumen is employed in preparing CGBM mixes with viscosity grades VG30, VG40, or Polymer Modified Bitumen (PMB) as per IRC: SP-125 (2019). This study utilizes VG30 Bitumen to prepare a bituminous blend. A range of bitumen test properties was conducted and presented in Table 3.

Porous Bitumen Mix Design

Before proceeding with the preparation of Bituminous Mixes, it is essential to determine the Bitumen content suitable for the chosen aggregate gradation. To achieve this, the Drain Down test, following the guidelines outlined in ASTM D 6390, is conducted. The procedure involves weighing the empty basket first and then creating a bituminous mix of 1200 grams of the selected aggregate gradation, initially mixed with 3.5% of bitumen. Subsequently, the basket with the sample is positioned within an oven set at a temperature range of 120 – 175 °C, with a catching plate positioned below the basket. The initial weight of the catching plate is recorded before testing, as depicted in Fig 2. A waiting period of one hour is allowed to permit the bitumen to drain down. After this duration, the drain-down percentage is calculated by measuring the quantity of bitumen drained onto the catching plate, as illustrated in Fig 3.

Table 3. Test results of bitumen

S. No	Test Performed	Codal Specification	Test Results	Specified Limit (as per IS: 73 2013)
1	Penetration Value (mm)	IS:1203 Part (4)	66	65-70
2	Ductility (cm)	IS:1208 (1978)	79	Not less than 75
3	Softening point (°C)	IS:1205 (1978)	52	40 -55°C
4	Flashpoint (°C)	IS:1209 (1978)	245	Min 220
5	Fire point (°C)	IS:1209 (1978)	260	Min 220

Fig 2: Wire basket with bituminous mix placed in the oven.

The Optimum Binder content is established based on a drain-down percentage of less than 0.3%. In the case of a drain-down ratio measuring 0.29, the Bitumen content is determined to be 4.65%, as depicted in Figure 3. Compaction Procedure: The compaction process employed a hammer equipped with a flat, circular tamping face weighing 4.9 kg, and it included a sliding weight to facilitate a free fall from a height of 45 cm. To ascertain the most effective compaction effort, the mixture underwent compaction using a marshal compactor, with a systematic variation in the compaction effort. This variation was designed to yield a corresponding void ratio within the 25-35% range. For Marshall-sized samples with dimensions of 100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height, the compaction effort consisted of 46 blows.

Fig 3: Graph representing Drain down Test

Preparation of Grout

According to Sunil and Naga Kumar (2020), the performance and durability of CGBM, or open-graded bituminous mixes filled with grouts, are influenced by several key characteristics. These include the grouting rate, saturation degree, and residual air voids. These factors significantly determine how well CGBM can withstand traffic loads and

various climatic conditions. According to the recommendations provided in IRC SP -125 (2019), it is advisable to maintain an air void content of 2 to 3% in the CGBM composite after seven days, as this helps prevent potential leakage of the asphalt binder, especially under high-temperature conditions. The formulation of various grout slurries adheres to the guidelines outlined in IRC SP 125 – 2019. Materials used to prepare grout slurry: The fundamental constituents employed are cement, sand, and water. Table 4 presents the initial and final setting times of the three distinct varieties of cement utilized in mortar preparation:

1. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC)
2. Portland Pozzolana Cement (PPC)
3. Rapid Hardening Cement (RHC)

Table 4: Initial and final setting time of Cements.

Cement	Codal specification	Initial setting time (minutes)	Final setting time (minutes)	Codal specified limit	
				Initial time(min)	Final time(min)
OPC	IS:12269 (1987)	26	450	30	600
PPC	IS: 1489 (2015)	24.5	408	30	600
RHC	IS: 8041 (1990)	5.2	390	30	600

Tests on Grouts

In the present investigation, the grout formulated using conventional Portland cement is denoted as OG. Likewise, the grout made with Portland Pozzolana cement is called PG, while the grout incorporating Rapid Hardening cement is designated as RG. The flow cone test is a method used to measure the flowability of a material. The Compressive Strength test is a method used to determine the ability of a material to withstand compressive forces.

Flow Cone Test This testing procedure offers a means of determining the efflux time, in seconds, for a specified volume of grout slurry as it flows through a standardized flow cone. It is a versatile method applicable to laboratory and field settings (WSDOT Test Method for ASTM C 939). The time it takes for the grout to efflux directly indicates its flowability. As per IRC SP: 125 2019, the recommended efflux time, or flow value, falls within 20 to 50 seconds. Specific values for the flow and the cement + sand water ratio are provided in Table 5:

Table 5. Results for Flow value and Cement + Sand to water ratio

Type of Grout	Flow value (sec)	Cement + Sand / Water ratio
PG	35	0.26
OG	36	0.27
RG	35	0.45

Compressive strength of Grout The binder components in the mixtures must exhibit a certain level of strength that enables them to endure external loads. The aggregates incorporated into a pavement are the primary source of its strength. Therefore, the compressive strength of the grout slurries is evaluated. As per the specifications stated in IRC SP: 125 (2019), the suggested compressive strength for grout after 28 days generally lies within the interval of 40 to 100 N/mm². The assessment follows the ASTM C 109 (2020) standard, with 50 mm cube specimens examined at the three and 28 days. A homogeneous blend of sand and cement is employed in a 1:1 proportion. To mitigate the issue of grout leaking, it is recommended to utilize thin polythene bags. In addition, a layer of wax or grease is administered onto the surfaces of the mould to enhance the simplicity of extracting the dried grout. Fig 4 illustrates the compressive strength of several samples at both the three-day and 28-day time intervals.

Fig 4: Comparing the compressive strength of grouts.

Preparation of CGBM samples

Equipment required for the preparation of CGBM samples

A heating source with a minimum temperature of 200°C is essential to prepare the bitumen samples. The oven used must have a capacity to maintain a temperature of at least 170°C. A bitumen mixer or mixing bowl is necessary for blending the sample at 130°C. The sample is compacted within split molds available in two sizes: one with a 100mm diameter and 63mm height and another with a 100mm diameter and 200mm height. A 4.5 kg rammer with a free fall of 49 cm is employed to compact the sample within the molds. The grout is mixed in the required proportions using a grout mixer. In preparation for sample creation, the surface of the molds is coated with wax or oil to facilitate easy removal. Since high-temperature mixing demands safety precautions, including heat-resistant gloves and shoes, special care must be taken when handling and preparing the samples. The preparation of CGBM samples follows the guidelines presented in IRC SP:125 (2019), involving two distinct phases:

- 1) Bituminous Mix Preparation
- 2) Grout Slurry Preparation

In the initial phase, the Bitumen is heated to a temperature range of 150 to 170°C, while the aggregates undergo oven drying at 110°C. Subsequently, the oven-dried aggregates are placed in a bituminous mixer or mixing bowl, and hot bitumen, optimized for the binder content, is added to the aggregates. The freshly prepared hot high-void bituminous mix is then uniformly filled into the molds in accordance with the design mix specifications. Compaction must be completed within 3 minutes, ensuring that the mix temperature remains within the specified standards, as illustrated in Fig 5, step I.

Bitumen is heated for mixing

Step I: Bituminous mix preparation

Step II: Grout slurry preparation

Step III: Cement grout bituminous mix preparation

Fig 5: Step-by-Step Procedure of CGBM sample preparation

After the compacted mixture has cooled to room temperature (approximately 50-60°C), the cementitious grout can be poured slowly onto the surface and, if necessary, evenly spread using a small scraper or brush. To prevent potential grout leakage, the outer corners and edges of the molds can be sealed with polythene covers or by applying a wax coating. The grouting process relies on natural gravitational force, but gentle vibrational compaction is administered to ensure complete penetration of the grout to the full depth, as depicted in Fig 5. Following 24 hours, the grouted mixture is removed from the molds and subjected to a curing process lasting at least three days using dampened jute bags.

The terminology used for the different types of cement used in the preparation for the CGBM mix is as follows:

1. Portland Pozzolana-Cement Grouted Bitumen Mix (PGBM)
2. Ordinary Portland-Cement Grouted Bitumen Mix (OGBM)
3. Rapid Hardening-Cement Grouted Bitumen Mix (RGBM)

Volumetrics of CGBM Mixes Following the production of CGBM mixes, retaining specific voids within the samples is crucial. This is done to facilitate bitumen expansion at elevated temperatures and to allow the samples to adjust naturally during compression. The recommended air voids in the CGBM mix should amount to at least 2 to 3 percent after a seven-day curing period. In alignment with IRC SP: 125 (2019) guidelines, the voids in samples after seven days of curing are advised to be within the 2 to 3 percent range. After seven days of curing for CGBM samples, the calculation of air voids involves determining the grout's volumetrics relative to the CGBM samples' volumetrics. Reference to the volumetrics of bituminous mixes, detailed in Fig 6, aids in comprehending the constituents of CGBM composites.

Fig 6: Phase diagram for CGBM mixes.

Were,
 W_{bm} : Weight of Bituminous mix (before grouting)

V_a : Volume of air voids in the compacted bituminous mix
 V_{bo} : Volume of bituminous mix only, i.e., without air voids
 V_b : Volume of Bitumen in the mix
 V_{ag} : Volume of aggregates in the mix
 W_b : Weight of Bitumen in the mix
 W_{ag} : Weight of Aggregate in the mix
 W_g : Weight of Grout in the CGBM mix.
 V_g : Volume of grout in the mix
 V_a' : Volume of air voids after seven days in the CGBM mix.
 W : Weight of the total CGBM mix
 W' : Weight of the CGBM mix after seven days.
 V : Volume of CGBM Mix
 e : Percentage of air voids in the bituminous mix
 e' : Percentage of air voids in the cement grouted mix.

The percentage of air voids (e) in the bituminous mix is calculated by using Equation 1,

$$e = \frac{G_{mm} - G_{mb}}{G_{mm}} \quad (1)$$

Where G_{mm} is the theoretical maximum specific gravity,
 G_{mb} is bulk-specific gravity.

The volume of air voids (V_a) is calculated by using Equation 2,

$$V_a = \frac{\text{percentage air voids}}{100} \times \text{Total volume of bitumen mix} \quad (2)$$

The volume of the bitumen mix (V_{bo}) is calculated by using the equation 3,

$$V_{bo} = (\text{Total volume of the bitumen mix}) - (\text{Volume of the air voids}) \quad (3)$$

The volume of the aggregate in the mix (V_a') is calculated by using the equation 4,

$$V_a' = \frac{\text{Mass of aggregate in the mix}}{\text{Specific gravity in the mix}} \quad (4)$$

The mass of bitumen in the mix (W_{bm}) is calculated by using Equation 5,

$$W_{bm} = (\text{percentage of bitumen in the mix}) \times (\text{Total mass of mix}) \quad (5)$$

The mass of the aggregate in the mix (W) is calculated by using Equation 6,

$$W = (\text{Total mass of mix}) - (\text{Mass of bitumen in the mix}) \quad (6)$$

The composite structure of the material makes it difficult to precisely ascertain the volume of grout in the CGBM samples after a 7-day cure. To determine the absolute volume of grout, a measured quantity of grout is poured into a mold or cup to estimate the grout volume in the mix. The approximate bulk-specific gravity is then calculated and detailed in Table 6. Subsequently, the volume of air voids in the CGBM mix is computed by assessing the difference between the volume of air voids before grouting and the volume of grout in the CGBM mix after seven days.

Tests and Results

Compressive Strength Test

During this test, cylindrical samples measuring 100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height are fabricated, following which compression testing is conducted in accordance with ASTM D 1075 (2007) standards. This method entails subjecting molded cylindrical samples to a compressive load applied at a controlled rate of 0.2kN/sec, maintained within a specified range until failure occurs, as illustrated in Fig 7. The compressive strength of the specimen is determined by dividing the peak load by its cross-sectional area at the fracture point.

Fig 7: Compression testing of samples: (a) Preparation of sample before testing, (b) sample during testing, and (c) sample after testing

The automatic digital machine was employed to assess the compressive strength of CGBM samples, ensuring precision in the results. Samples were prepared using molds of 100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height. Testing was conducted at three days and 28 days to evaluate the compression strength characteristics of the CGBM samples. As RG is used as the grout, testing was performed for three days to understand its early strength after grouting. The results indicated that RGBM samples exhibited nearly twice the strength of the other two samples at the three-day mark. Upon reviewing the graph presented in Fig 8 for the 28 days, it is evident that RGBM retains a higher level of compressive strength than the other two variants. Regarding compressive strength, RGBM emerges as the preferable choice over the other two choices. However, considering that rapid-hardening cement comes at a higher cost than OPC and PPC, the selection might be influenced by cost considerations. If early strength is not a critical factor, either of the two samples, OGBM or PGBM, could be viable options since they exhibit the recommended compressive strength as per IRC SP 125 (>5 N/mm²). All specimens demonstrated compressive strength surpassing the specified value in IRC SP 125 (2019). Specifically, RGBM exhibited greater strength at the three-day mark than other mixed proportions. By the seventh day, all mix proportions showcased nearly identical levels of strength.

Marshall Stability and Flow Tests

Marshall stability is characterized by the load achieved when the loading rate decreases to the extent that the deformation versus stability(load) curve levels out horizontally. The Marshall stability test is carried out in accordance with ASTM D 6927-15 and ASTM D 1075. Two sets of conditioned and unconditioned samples are prepared for each mix. Marshall retained stability is calculated by dividing the Marshall stability value for the conditioned samples by that of the unconditioned samples, as illustrated in equation (7).

$$\text{Retained Stability (\%)} = \frac{S_2}{S_1} \times 100 \tag{7}$$

Where:

S₁ is the Marshal stability of unconditioned (dry) samples.

S₂ is the Marshal stability of Conditioned samples.

Fig 8: Comparison of compression strength between the samples at three days and 28 days

(a)

According to Fig 9, it is evident that the Marshall stability of RGBM samples at three days is higher in both scenarios, exhibiting a 42% increase from 3 days to 28 days. Similarly, PGBM samples demonstrated an increase of almost 150%, and OGBM exhibited a growth of over 180% in stability over the same period. This indicates that OGBM samples have a higher stability value, which can be sustained for an extended duration. Consequently, OGBM emerges as the most favorable option regarding stability value among all the alternatives.

(b)

Fig 9: Marshall stability of CGM samples (a) 3 days (b) 28 days

Indirect Tensile Strength Test

A cylindrical specimen undergoes loading along its vertical diametral axis at a specified deformation rate (50mm/min) and test temperature (25 °C) to ascertain the Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS) of CGBM samples. The recorded peak load at the point of failure is then used to calculate the specimen's indirect tensile strength. The ITS test adheres to the guidelines outlined in ASTM D 6931 (2012), as depicted in Fig 10.

Fig10: Indirect tensile strength test (a) Before testing (b) After testing

Figure 11 compares various materials tested in Indirect Tensile Strength (ITS). The data suggests that CGBM-RG exhibits superior strength at three days compared to PGBM and OGBM. By the 28th day, PGBM and OGBM mix proportions display nearly identical strength, whereas the rapid-hardening grouted mix shows relatively less strength. The Indirect Tensile Strength at 28 days indicates that the PPC and OPC grouted bitumen mix achieves its strength later, lasting comparatively longer than the RHC.

Durability Tests

In accordance with ASTM D 7064, the Cantabro Test is conducted to assess the durability of CGBM samples, utilizing a Los Angeles abrasion testing machine without steel balls. This test evaluated cohesion, bonding indirectly, and the effects of traffic abrasion (wear and tear) on all three types of CGBM samples utilized in this study (Hassani et al., 2020). Prior to abrasion testing, Marshall samples undergo conditioning for 6 hours at 25°C. The abrasion loss resulting from the wear and tear action is quantified as the weight loss of the samples, expressed as a percentage of their initial weight. Fig 12 illustrates the conditions before and after the abrasion tests. The Cantabro test is conducted in a Los Angeles machine (ASTM C131) without metal balls and in conformity with AASHTO TP 108 (2014) and BS EN 12697 (2017). The open graded aggregates mixtures with different fibers and asphalt binder content are prepared and rotated in the cylinder for 300 rounds with a 30–33 rpm speed.

Fig 11: Comparison of Indirect Tensile strength of samples at three days and 28 days

Fig 12: Durability test (a) Before testing (b) After testing

As depicted in Fig 13, the abrasion loss percentages are 23.11%, 23.84%, and 20.74% for PGBM, OGBM, and RGBM, respectively. Consequently, all the samples exhibit satisfactory abrasion values. Notably, RGBM experienced a lower percentage loss of its constituents during abrasion testing. This could be attributed to the high heat of hydration in rapid-hardening cement. During grouting, the bonding between the bituminous mix and grout initiates early strength gain and sets rapidly.

Fig 13: Comparison of PGBM, OGBM, & RGBM for abrasion

The recorded abrasion losses are 23.11%, 23.84%, and 20.74% for PGBM, OGBM, and RGBM, respectively, indicating that all samples possess satisfactory abrasion values. Notably, RGBM demonstrated a lower percentage loss of constituents during abrasion testing. This is likely attributed to the high heat of hydration in rapid-hardening cement, enabling early strength gain and swift setting of the bonding between the bituminous mix and grout during pouring.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study aimed to assess the strength and composition of grouted mixes prepared with different types of cement. Adhering to IRC SP – 125 (2019) guidelines for Gradation II aggregates, it was crucial to maintain voids in the Bituminous mix within the specified range of 25 to 35%. This required an optimum binder content of 4.65% and a compaction effort of 46 blows for samples with dimensions of 100 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height.

- The investigation revealed that RGBM exhibited remarkable characteristic strength at three days (7.02 N/mm²), surpassing PGBM (4.07 N/mm²) and OGBM (3.53 N/mm²) by nearly twice. Consequently, Rapid Hardening Cement in CGBM is recommended for early pavement construction, ensuring higher compressive strength from the initial days.
- While RGBM demonstrated greater compressive strength (9.10 N/mm²) compared to PGBM (8.92 N/mm²) and CGBM-OG (8.06 N/mm²), all samples met IRC SP – 125 (2019) recommended values, making any of them suitable as grouting material.
- Analyzing Marshal stability values, unconditioned PGBM samples exhibited superior stability (84.13 kN) compared to OGBM (82.18 kN) and RGBM (78.91 kN), yet all values exceeded the acceptable threshold of 60 kN according to IRC SP 125 (2019). However, conditioning at 60 °C for 24 hours revealed a decline in stability for RGBM below the desired 60 kN, whereas PGBM and OGBM maintained values above this threshold. Moreover, the percentage of reattained stability for RGBM at 28 days was lower than the other two.

In summary, the study suggests that using rapid hardening cement in bitumen mix proportions yields superior overall strength. Therefore, the RGBM mix proportion is recommended for colder regions or places with crucial early strength. At the same time, PGBM and OGBM are suitable for normal Indian conditions and provide later strength.

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